

Wood-resin compatibility model. Mechanical wood characterization to assign a resistance class according to the UNE-EN 338 standard.

Introduction

The incorporation of complementary activities to the exploitation of timber can represent an improvement in the management and conservation of forests, as well as allowing the generation of regular economic activities that create added social value for the populations benefiting from different products. One of the complementary activities listed for Galicia in Decree 73/2020 of 24 April is the use of resin in three pine species (*Pinus pinaster* Ait., *Pinus radiata* D. Don and *Pinus nigra* Arnold) before the clear-felling.

Approach and main results

In this context, there is an interest in including tapping activity as an ecosystem service added to the management of Galician mountains, initially planted for timber use only. As a material of natural origin, wood presents a great deal of variability. The characterization and classification processes are presented with the aim of complying with the basic requirements established by regulations for the appropriate use of wood as a structural element, which consists, fundamentally, in knowing the properties of the material. In this sense, one of the proposals of the ACREMA Operative Group was to evaluate the influence of the resin activity on the quality of wood from a structural point of view. For this purpose, mechanical tests (static bending) were carried out on a total of 238 pieces of *Pinus pinaster* with structural dimensions, separated into two subsamples (resin-treated and control logs). Prior to the breakage (bending) tests, all the boards were visually graded according to the criteria established in the Spanish visual grading regulations for coniferous wood. During the visual grading process, the presence of some singularities that may affect the structural strength of the wood were analysed: knots, resin pockets, cracks, deformations. However, the number of rejected tapped boards is quite similar to the number of rejected boards from control logs. Structural strength values for all the material were obtained from the mechanical tests and it was possible to compare the structural quality of the wood from previously tapped and untapped logs. In general, the values obtained for the two samples are in the same order. Regarding the strength, the sample of boards from the control logs had a slightly (6 %) higher average value than the sample of boards from the tapped trees. The average values of the strength properties: modulus of elasticity, bending strength and density, showed no numerically significant differences between the tapped and control material from the two plots. The study concluded that the resin does not cause any loss in the mechanical

properties of the wood (strength and stiffness). With regard to the density parameter, however, an increase in the value is observed in the wood from tapped pieces, which could mean positive contributions from a structural point of view. The characteristic values of the strength properties of the tapped wood obtained are within the expected range for Spanish *Pinus pinaster* wood, which is nowadays accepted in the European standard that regulates the use of wood species for structural purposes (EN 1912).

Lessons learned

The use of resin in the Galician community presents a series of weaknesses that hinder the development of the sector, from the scarce availability of workers in the trade to the rejection of forest owners due to the possible effects of the use of resin on the quality of the wood, to the lack of confidence on the part of the manufacturing industry due to possible problems in the technical handling of the material.

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

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<https://acrema.es/r4-asignacion-de-una-clase-resistente-a-la-madera-de-p-pinaster-resinada-con-fines-estructurales-segun-la-norma->

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